

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF BROILER CHICKS FED GRADED LEVELS OF WHITE GUINEA CORN AS A REPLACEMENT FOR MAIZE

Ibe, E.A., Bulus, E.D., Ogundipe, S.O. and Duru, S.

Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

ABSTRACT

The experiment was conducted to evaluate the effects of replacing 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 % levels of maize in broiler diet with white guinea corn on the growth performance of broiler birds at starter and finisher phases of production. Substituting maize with white guinea corn did not adversely ($p > 0.05$) affect feed intake across the dietary treatments at both the starter and finisher phases of the study. At the starter phase, birds fed 25 % and 50 % guinea corn as replacement for maize gave comparable results as those fed diet T₁ (control). At the finisher phase, there was no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference for final weight, daily weight gain, feed conversion ratios and cost of feed per kilogramme weight gain between the birds fed the control diet and those fed between 25 % and 75 % maize replacement by white guinea corn. Birds fed 100 % white guinea corn based diet gave significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowest values in all parameters measured and poor feed conversion ratio. From the results of this study, it was concluded that white guinea corn could conveniently replace up to 75 % of maize in broiler starter and finisher diets respectively without any adverse effect on growth performance.

KEYWORDS: White guinea corn, Maize, Broiler chicks, animal protein, broiler starter, broiler finisher.

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Corresponding Author: ezzy1512@yahoo.co.uk

INTRODUCTION

In a developing country like Nigeria, there is an inadequate supply of animal protein sources. An average Nigerian consumes only about 8.6 g of animal protein per day as against 53.3g by the inhabitants of developed countries (Ogundipe, 1996 and Ojo, 2003). Sanni and Ogundipe (2005) reported that poultry industry occupies a major position in the livestock sector of agricultural production because birds reproduce much quicker to produce meats and eggs for human consumption within the shortest possible time. According to Ogundipe and Sanni (2002) and FAO (2006) reports, poultry is considered to be a means of livelihood and a way of achieving a certain level of economic independence of Nigeria. Adebola (2004) reported that 41.23% of animal protein yield per annum in Nigeria is sourced from poultry (meat and eggs), 9.79% from cattle and 12.43% from pigs. FAO (1995) reported that the best logical solution to Nigeria's meat scarcity is to increase broiler chicken production. Nutrition is perhaps the most important consideration in livestock management. Inadequate supply of feeds, nutritionally unbalanced rations, adulterated ingredients or stale feeds are some of the factors responsible for low productivity of livestock in tropics (Ogundipe, 1987 and Ogundipe *et al.*, 2003). Apart from nutrition, Poultry industry contributes significantly to family income (Ogundipe and Sanni, 2002). Therefore the major interest of the farmer is to reduce the feed cost, which accounts for 60 to 70% of the total cost of production (Igwebuike *et al.*, 2001 and Ogundipe, *et al.*; 2003). Research efforts are geared towards evaluating alternative feed ingredients for poultry. According to Atteh and Ologbenla (1993), such alternatives should have comparative nutritive value but cheaper than the conventional protein and energy sources. They should also be available in large quantities.

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Maize is used for other purposes such as biofuel, brewing, starch industries and human consumption. However, inadequate production of this grain and the intense competition for maize between man, industries and livestock especially in the drier areas of the tropics has made poultry rations to be expensive (Asha Rajini *et al.*, 1986 and FAO, 2006). This situation forces the search for other alternative energy sources which are available in large quantities and are cheaper, such as guinea corn (*Sorghum bicolor*, Linn.), finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*) and pearl millet (*Pennisetum typhoides*). Worldwide, guinea corn and millet grain crops are very important ingredients in poultry diets. They both have over 90% of the feeding value of maize (Rooney, 1990). Guinea corn and millets are the most widely grown cereal crops that have been successfully cultivated in the semi-arid regions of Asia and Africa since prehistoric times and their cost are relatively less in the areas of cultivation with little industrial uses in Nigeria. (Ravindran and Blair, 1991 and Nyannor *et al.*, 2007). The protein in millets is well balanced in limiting amino acids for practical poultry diets. Lysine, Methionine and Cystine contents in finger millet is about 2.86%, 1.75% and 1.51% of the Crude protein (Rachie and Peters, 1997). Therefore their incorporation in place of maize can reduce the dependency on maize and also the cost of poultry production. This study is aimed at evaluating the performance of broiler chickens fed two varieties each of guinea corn and millets as replacement for dietary maize.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location of the study

The study was conducted at the poultry unit of the Department of Animal Science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria in Nigeria, located within the Northern Guinea Savannah Zone on the latitude 11° 9' 45'' N and longitude 7° 38' 8'' E, at an altitude of 610 m above sea level (Ovimaps, 2012).

Sources of the Experimental Materials

The guinea corn and millet grains used in these studies were purchased from the local farmers in Samaru, Zaria while other ingredients were sourced from Rebson feed mill, Zaria, Kaduna State.

Experimental diets for feeding trial

Five isonitrogenous and isocaloric diets (23.5% CP; 2800 Kcal/kg ME) and (21.5% CP; 2900 Kcal/kg) for the broiler starter and finisher phases were formulated as follows:

Diet 1 (T1) contained 0% guinea corn + 100% maize (Control)

Diet 2 (T2) contained 25% guinea corn + 75% maize

Diet 3 (T3) contained 50% guinea corn + 50% maize

Diet 4 (T4) contained 75% guinea corn + 25% maize and

Diet 5 (T5) contained 100% guinea corn + 0% maize respectively.

The diets were formulated to be iso-nitrogenous and iso-caloric (23.5% CP; 2800 Kcal/kg ME) and (21.5% CP; 2900 Kcal/kg) for the broiler starter and finisher phases respectively (Table 1 and 3) respectively.

Experimental design and management of birds

A total of two hundred and twenty five (225) day-old Marshal broiler chicks (mixed sex) were purchased from Zarm farm in Kwara State. On arrival, the chicks were weighed and randomly assigned into five groups of 45 birds each. Each group was subdivided into 3 replicates of 15 birds in a completely randomized design (CRD). Each group was randomly assigned to the 5 experimental diets. All necessary and routine management practices and the recommended vaccinations were strictly observed throughout the period of this study. Feed and water were provided *ad libitum* during the trial period. The birds were weighed at the beginning of the trial and weekly thereafter. Weight gain, feed intake, leftover feeds were measured and recorded; feed conversion ratio, feed cost per kilogramme and cost per kilogramme weight gain and per cent mortality were calculated. The experiment lasted for 56 days.

Data Collection

The birds were weighed at the beginning of the experiment and weekly thereafter. Data were collected on initial weight, final body weight, average daily weight gain, feed intake and leftover feeds were measured. Feed

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conversion ratio, feed cost per kilogramme and the cost of feed per kilogramme weight gain (₦/kg) were calculated and mortality rate was recorded as it occurred. The experiment lasted for 8 weeks.

Statistical Analysis

All the data collected from the experiment were statistically analyzed using the General Linear Model Procedure of Statistical Analysis (SAS, 2002) software package. Significant difference between treatments means were separated by Duncan Multiple Range Test.

The model used for this design is as follows:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + t_i + e_{ij}$$

Where

- Y_{ij} = Individual observation.
 μ = Overall mean.
 t_i = Effect of treatment diets.
 e_{ij} = Experimental error.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Percentage composition of the experimental broiler starter diets for feeding trial (0-4 weeks)

Ingredients	Experimental diets/Levels of inclusion of white guinea corn				
	Diet 1 (T1) (0 %)	Diet 2 (T2) (25 %)	Diet 3 (T3) (50 %)	Diet 4 (T4) (75 %)	Diet 5 (T5) (100 %)
Maize	47.35	35.52	23.68	11.84	0.00
White guinea corn	0.00	11.84	23.68	35.52	47.35
Maize offal	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
GNC	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00
Soya cake	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00
Fish meal	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Limestone	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Palm oil	1.05	1.50	1.79	1.87	2.00
Table salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Vit/M. Premix	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
L-Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
DL- Methionine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Total	100	100	100	100	100
Calculated Analysis :					
ME(Kcal/kg)	2882	2882	2882	2883	2883
Crude Protein (%)	23.50	23.50	23.50	23.50	23.50
Ether Extract (%)	5.60	6.03	6.07	6.03	6.03
Crude fibre (%)	3.90	3.92	3.93	3.94	3.96
Calcium (%)	1.29	1.29	1.29	1.29	1.30
Avail. Phosphorus (%)	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.64
Lysine (%)	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.27
Methionine (%)	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46
Methionine +Cystine(%)	0.93	0.92	0.92	0.91	0.90
Feed Cost/kg (₦/kg)	94.77	96.68	96.05	95.41	96.82

*Bio Mix Chicks provided the following per kg diet: Vit. A 2500i.u; Vit.D₃, 500i.u; Vit. E 5.75; Vit. K₃ 0.5mg; Vit. B₁ 0.45mg; Vit B₂ 1.25mg; Niacin 6.875mg; Pantothenic Acid 1.875mg; Vit. B₆ 0.75mg; Vit. B₁₂ 0.00375mg; Folic Acid 0.1875mg; Biotin H₂ 0.015mg; Choline Chloride 75mg; Cobalt 0.05mg; Copper 0.75mg; Iodine 0.25mg; Iron 5mg; Manganese 10mg; Selenium 0.05mg; Zinc 7.5mg; Antioxidant 0.3125mg.

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Table 2: Performance characteristics of broiler chicks fed graded levels of white guinea corn as a replacement for maize (0-4 weeks)

Parameters	Experimental Diets/Level of white guinea corn inclusion					SEM
	Diet 1 (T1) 0%	Diet 2 (T2) 25%	Diet 3 (T3) 50%	Diet 4 (T4) 75%	Diet 5 (T5) 100%	
Initial weight (g/bird)	40.63	40.57	40.68	40.64	40.66	0.08
Final weight (g/bird)	1031.11 ^a	999.44 ^a	978.68 ^{ab}	910.00 ^{ab}	860.00 ^b	63.70
Av. Total weight gain (g/bird)	990.48 ^a	958.87 ^a	938.00 ^{ab}	869.35 ^{ab}	819.34 ^b	63.67
Av. Daily weight gain(g/bird/day)	35.37 ^a	34.24 ^a	33.50 ^{ab}	31.04 ^{ab}	29.26 ^b	2.27
Total feed intake (g/bird)	1585.56	1550.11	1546.67	1546.11	1535.56	47.39
Daily feed intake (g/bird/day)	56.62	55.36	55.23	55.21	54.84	1.69
Feed conversion ratio	1.61 ^a	1.61 ^a	1.67 ^a	1.79 ^b	1.88 ^b	0.11
Cost of feed/kg weight gain (₦)	152.66 ^a	156.40 ^a	160.65 ^{ab}	171.10 ^b	182.00 ^b	11.67

^{abcd}Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different.

SEM: standard error of mean.

Table 2 shows the performance characteristics of broiler bird (0-4 weeks) fed broiler starter feed with graded levels of white guinea corn as replacement for maize. Substituting maize with white guinea corn did not adversely ($p > 0.05$) affect daily feed intake and total feed intake across the treatments. There was no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference between the birds fed the control diet and those fed between 25% and 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn in most of the parameters measured. There was however significant reduction in performance for birds fed 100% replacement of maize by white guinea corn. There was no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference for feed conversion ratios of birds fed up to 50% of maize replacement by white guinea corn.

Substituting maize with white guinea corn did not adversely ($p > 0.05$) affect daily feed intake across the treatments. Birds fed 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn had significantly ($p < 0.05$) poor performance in all the parameters measured.

There was no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference for feed conversion ratios of birds fed up to 50% of maize replacement by white guinea corn. These observations agreed with the report of Cullison (1987) and Reddy *et al.* (2008) who reported that 50% replacement of maize with guinea corn did not impair body weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio of broiler starter when compared with maize based diet. Also, Makled and Afifi (2001) indicated that feed conversion ratio of broiler chicks at 6 weeks of age showed that 50% of the dietary maize can be replaced by guinea corn.

The poor performance of birds fed diet T₅ (with 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn) might be due to poor nutrient digestibility as a result of the presence of antinutritional factor (oxalate) compared to the maize based diet. This observation is in agreement with the reports of Cao *et al.* (1998), who stated that digestibility of nutrients were less for soft guinea corn (white guinea corn) than for medium (red or yellow) and hard (cream) guinea corn. And also with the reports of Adeola (2006) who observed that growing chicks fed 100% guinea corn based diet had the lowest growth performance. However, Thakur *et al.* (1985) and Elkin *et al.* (1991) claimed no adverse effects of low-tannin guinea corn on broiler performance.

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Table 3: Percentage composition of the experimental broiler finisher diets for feeding trial 2 (5-8 weeks)

Ingredients	Experimental diets/Levels of inclusion of white guinea corn				
	Diet 1 (T1) 0 %	Diet 2 (T2) 25 %	Diet 3 (T3) 50 %	Diet 4 (T4) 75 %	Diet 5 (T5) 100 %
Maize	52.70	39.53	26.35	13.17	0.00
White guinea corn	0.00	13.17	26.35	39.53	52.70
Maize offal	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
GNC	22.50	22.50	22.50	22.50	22.50
Soya cake	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Fish meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Limestone	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Palm oil	1.05	1.50	1.73	1.96	2.10
Table salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Vit/M. Premix	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
L-Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
DL- Methionine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Calculated Analysis :					
ME(Kcal/kg)	2932	2933	2933	2933	2933
Crude Protein (%)	21.50	21.50	21.50	21.50	21.50
Ether Extract (%)	5.88	6.08	5.99	5.96	5.92
Crude fibre (%)	4.13	4.13	4.14	4.15	4.16
Calcium (%)	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
Avail. Phosphorus (%)	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60
Lysine (%)	1.15	1.15	1.15	1.15	1.14
Methionine (%)	0.46	0.46	0.47	0.46	0.46
Methionine +Cystine (%)	0.87	0.86	0.86	0.85	0.84
Feed Cost/kg (₦/kg)	92.16	92.56	92.96	93.36	93.75

*Bio Mix Broiler finisher provided the following per kg diet: Vit. A 2500i.u; Vit.D₃, 500i.u; Vit. E 5.75; Vit. K₃ 0.5mg; Vit. B₁ 0.45mg; Vit B₂ 1.25mg; Niacin 6.875mg; Pantothenic Acid 1.875mg; Vit. B₆ 0.75mg; Vit. B₁₂ 0.00375mg; Folic Acid 0.1875mg; Biotin H₂ 0.015mg; Choline Chloride 75mg; Cobalt 0.05mg; Copper 0.75mg; Iodine 0.25mg; Iron 5mg; Manganese 10mg; Selenium 0.05mg; Zinc 7.5mg; Antioxidant 0.3125mg.

Table 4: Performance characteristics of broiler finisher fed graded levels of white guinea corn as replacement for maize (5-8 weeks)

Parameters	Dietary treatments/replacement levels					SEM
	Diet 1 (T1) 0%	Diet 2 (T2) 25%	Diet 3 (T3) 50%	Diet 4 (T4) 75%	Diet 5 (T5) 100%	
	Initial weight (g/bird)	1007.33	1009.71	1008.14	1009.77	
Final weight (g/bird)	2275.56 ^a	2241.11 ^a	2281.66 ^a	2205.66 ^{ab}	2114.44 ^b	54.10
Av. Total weight gain (g/bird)	1268.22 ^a	1231.40 ^a	1273.52 ^a	1196.88 ^{ab}	1105.77 ^b	54.20
Av. Daily weight gain (g/bird/day)	60.39 ^a	58.63 ^a	60.64 ^a	56.99 ^{ab}	52.66 ^b	2.58
Total feed intake (g/bird)	2960.60	2963.30	2879.40	2908.30	2915.60	104.10
Daily feed intake (g/bird/day)	140.98	141.11	137.11	138.49	138.83	4.96
Feed conversion ratio	2.33 ^a	2.41 ^a	2.27 ^a	2.45 ^{ab}	2.63 ^b	0.09
Cost of feed/kg weight gain (₦)	215.38 ^a	223.19 ^{ab}	211.41 ^a	229.14 ^{ab}	246.95 ^b	9.23

SEM: standard error of mean.

^{abcd} Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly (P<0.05) different.

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Results of the performance characteristics are shown in Table 4. Feed intake did not differ ($p>0.05$) significantly across the treatments. Birds fed diet T₁ (0%) gave similar ($p>0.05$) values of weight gain as those fed diets T₂, T₃ and T₄ (with 25, 50 and 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn). Birds fed 50% replacement of maize with white guinea corn had numerically the highest daily weight gain (60.64 g) than birds fed the control, 25% and 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn (60.39, 58.63 and 56.99 respectively). Birds fed 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn had significantly ($p<0.05$) lower weight gain compared to other treatments.

The feed conversion ratio of birds fed 50% replacement of maize with white guinea corn was the best (2.27) but was not significantly ($p>0.05$) different from those fed control diet (2.33) and those fed 25% and 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn (2.41 and 2.45) respectively. The poorest value for feed conversion ratio was recorded in birds fed 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn (2.63).

The cost of feed per kilogramme increased with increasing levels of guinea corn in the diet. Feed cost in naira per kilogramme weight gain was lowest in birds fed 50% replacement of maize with white guinea corn (₦211.41) but was similar ($P > 0.05$) to those fed control (₦215.38) and those fed 25% and 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn (₦223.19 and ₦229.14) respectively. Birds fed diet 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn had the highest ($p < 0.05$) cost of feed per kilogramme weight gain (₦246.95).

Birds fed up to 75% replacement of maize with white guinea corn was comparable to those fed control diet in most of the parameters measured. There was significant ($p<0.05$) reduction in daily weight gain of birds fed 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn. This result agrees with the reports of Thakur *et al.* (1985); Rama Rao *et al.* (1995) and Jayanaik *et al.* (2008) who reported that 75% substitution of maize with guinea corn in broilers diet did not affect body weight gain, feed intake and feed conversion ratio. The poor feed conversion ratio and significant ($p<0.05$) reduction in weight gain of birds fed 100% replacement of maize with white guinea corn could be due to the high levels of oxalates found in the white guinea corn grain. The results agrees with the report of Adeola (2006) who observed lowest performance of broiler chickens fed 100% guinea corn and also the reports of Oke (1969) and Oboh (1986) who reported that oxalates affects calcium and magnesium metabolism. Oxalate also reacts with protein to form complexes which have an inhibitory effect on peptic digestion. Similarly, Attia (1998) reported that Giza-15 SG containing 0.397% tannins had insignificant effect on broiler growth during the period from 4 to 45 days of age.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of these studies and overall production period (0–56 days), the study reveals that White guinea corn could conveniently replace up to 75% of maize in broiler starter and finisher diets respectively without any adverse effect on growth performance characteristics.

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